

A UNIFIED APPROACH TO MODELING THE DAMAGE PROCESS OF COMPOSITE BEAMS UNDER STATIC, IMPACT AND CYCLIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

A unified model is proposed for simulating the damage and failure process of unidirectional composite beams subjected to static, low velocity impact, and cyclic loading. The model is based on the experimental finding that the damage mechanisms and failure modes of such beams under these loading conditions are noticeably similar. Progressive finite element analyses were carried out to simulate the entire failure process. Damaged elements in the compressive zone are assumed to retain a certain amount of the initial stiffness. The relationship between strength and strain rate, the accumulative damage rule, as well as the failure criterion are introduced in the simulation. The preliminary studies show that this model is feasible to predict some characteristics of beam under these loadings, such as stiffness, strength, toughness and fatigue life.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Cyclic Loading; Delamination; Low Velocity Impact; Material Characterization

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composites are multi-phase materials. The studies on failure mechanism of composites show that the damage and failure process under low velocity impact and cyclic loading are to some degree similar to that observed under static loading. In general, at first some micro-cracks occur at interfaces and in the weak phase (matrix). This indicates that

the initiation of incipient damage, which then causes stress redistribution in the reinforcement phase (fiber). Finally, breakage or kink occurs in the fibers resulting in macrofailure of the composite. This damage-failure mechanism is totally different from that which occurs in metals under cyclic and low velocity impact loading. In metals, failure is a consequence of initiation and propagation of main crack under cyclic loading, and the shift of toughness from ductile to brittle under impact loading.

One question arises from the above observation: Is it possible to establish a unified model to analyze and predict certain properties of composite materials, such as stiffness, strength, toughness and fatigue life? On the basis of studies on orthogonal laminates, K.L.Reifsnide et. al. proposed a characteristic damage state (CDS) (1), a critical element and subcritical element model (2), and a hybrid approach to composite life prediction (3), indicating that there indeed is a possibility to establish such a unified model. In this paper, through experimental and theoretical analyses of unidirectional composite beams subjected to three point bending under static, cyclic and low velocity impact loading, the authors attempt to establish a unified mechanics model to simulate the damage-failure process of composite beams. The findings are based on a total of 250 test specimens and progressive finite element analyses.

2. FAILURE MODES UNDER STATIC, IMPACT, AND CYCLIC LOADING

Unidirectional composite beams subjected to three point bending under static, low velocity impact and cyclic loading are studied. Figures 1a and 2 are the load-displacement curves of the specimens which experienced compressive damage-fiber breakage failure (Mode A), and compressive damage-interlaminar split failure (Mode B), respectively (4). The similarity in these two curves, up to the maximum load point B, is that the damage first occurs and then propagates in the compressive zone for specimens having either of these two failure modes. When the load is small, the relationship between load and displacement is linear. When the load is increased to a certain value, for instance, P_A , corresponding to points A in Figures 1 and 2, the crack in the direction of depth near the load point initiates, which results from the microbuckling of the surface fibers. The stiffness of the beam then starts to decrease. With increasing load, the damage continues to develop along the longitudinal and transversal directions, forming a ditched shape zone having two slopes under the load point. On the other hand, the difference between these two curves is that, in Figure 1, when the load reaches maximum point B, the fibers in tensile zone start to break, in the upward direction from the bottom, as a result of the tensile stress reaching the tensile strength of the fiber. Whereas, in Figure 2, when the maximum load point B is reached, the

specimen splits (delaminates) abruptly along the interlaminar in which the shear stress is maximum. Note that, at this time, the plane of maximum shear stress is no longer coincident with the midplane of the beam, but rather is located below the midplane. Consequently, the specimen loses most of its load carrying capacity.

Figure 1. Load-deflection curves of specimens having failure mode A
(a) Static, (b) Impact

Figure 2. Load-deflection curve of specimens having failure mode B

Figure 1b is the load-displacement curve of the specimen which experienced compressive damage-fiber breakage failure under impact loading (5). During impact, when the impact load reaches point A, the zone near the contact point is damaged because of the large compressive stress. Delamination and fiber breakage occur in this zone, resulting in a decrease of load. However, because the remaining portion is still capable of carrying load, the load carrying capacity of the beam is gradually reduced, allowing the development of damage in the compressive zone. When the tensile stress reaches the fiber strength in tension, fibers in the tensile zone start to break upward from the bottom surface, leading to complete loss of load carrying capacity.

For specimens under cyclic loading, failure mode is somewhat similar to that observed under static and low velocity impact loading. In one of the damage-failure modes, the stiffness decreases with fatigue damage in the compressive fibers. When the compressive damage extends to a considerably large zone, the interlaminar splitting in the plane of maximum shear stress takes place in an abrupt manner. In the other possible failure mode, damage first occurs and propagates in the compressive zone. When fatigued to a certain number of cycles, the fibers in the bottom surface start to break, and the breakage propagates rapidly upward, bringing about the complete failure of the specimen.

3. THE UNIFIED MODEL FOR DETERMINATION OF STIFFNESS, STRENGTH, TOUGHNESS AND FATIGUE LIFE

From the experimental observations, it can be seen that the damage mechanism and failure modes under the three different loading conditions have similar characteristics. In all cases, the damage first occurs in the compressive zone, and the duration of damage progress in this zone is quite long compared to the entire failure process of the specimen. The redistribution of stresses caused by the damaged zone results in additional damage. Owing to the characteristics of compressive zone, the damaged elements in this zone do not lose their stiffness entirely. Rather, they still participate in carrying the additional load increments. Based on these facts, it becomes possible to establish a unified model capable of simulating the damage process and determining the stiffness, strength, toughness and fatigue life of a beam.

The essential steps of the progressive failure analysis procedure can be described as follows. Determine the initial stress and displacement fields using finite element method. Introduce the relationship between the strength and strain rate, the accumulative damage rule, as well as the failure criterion. Then, identify the location and the load at which the damage initiates. Assume that the damaged elements retain a certain amount of their initial stiffness. Calculate the new stress and displacement fields for the proceeding load increments by accounting for the damaged elements. Repeat the procedure to simulate the entire process of failure.

It should be noted that, while creating a finite element mesh, a finer mesh is needed in the compressive zone, especially near the load point where damage first occurs. Its size should be compatible with the thickness of the layer and the wave length of the microbuckling of fibers. Whereas, the mesh size in other zones could be coarser.

3.1. Stiffness

The experiments on unidirectional composite beams indicate that a certain amount of degradation in stiffness takes place before maximum load is reached. This degradation is caused by the damage induced in the compressive zone. The initiation of damage is governed by the longitudinal compressive strength of the unidirectional composite material, σ_L^- . The value of σ_L^- could be obtained either from compressive tests of thin laminates, or predicted using the following equation (6),

$$\sigma_L^- = \frac{\frac{G_m}{1 - \nu_F}}{1 + \frac{\delta_0}{t} \frac{1}{r_m} \frac{1}{(1 - V_F)V_F} \sqrt{\frac{12G_m}{1 - V_F} \cdot \frac{1}{E_F V_F + E_m V_m}}} \quad (1)$$

Basic microfailure mode of composites in compression is the formation of a "kinking band" in the direction of the thickness of the specimen. In three point bending, however, because of the existence of stress gradient along the thickness, the microfailure of individual compressive elements does not lead to formation of a "kinking band" throughout the thickness. The compressive damage develops along the thickness and the longitudinal direction.

When the longitudinal compressive strength is reached in the composite material, it causes microbuckling of the fibers embedded in the shear-yielded matrix. Because of the localized nature of this failure mode, damaged elements still maintain their load carrying capacity. If a certain retention of stiffness in the damaged elements is assumed, the residual stiffness of the beam could be directly predicted from the displacement of the damaged beam and the corresponding load (4).

3.2. Strength

The redistribution of stresses occurs after damage is induced in the compressive zone. Using progressive failure analysis, the stress fields can be determined at each load increment (4). For the undamaged zone, using an appropriate failure criterion, the load at which the tensile or shear failure occurs, the corresponding deflection, and the absorbed energy in the beam can be predicted. In this study, the maximum tensile stress criterion and maximum shear stress criterion for the two aforementioned failure modes, respectively, are used.

We can also develop two simple equations using the beam theory for homogenous materials to approximately calculate the maximum tensile and shear stresses in the composite beam. We assume that, after damage, distributions of the normal bending and shear stresses in the undamaged zone are still linear and parabolic, respectively. Whereas, these two stresses in the damaged portion are assumed to be constant, σ^* (residual compressive strength) and zero, respectively. The maximum tensile stress, σ_{Lmax}^+ and maximum shear stress, τ_{max} in beams having a compressive damage zone can be calculated using the following equations (4),

Figure 3. Variation of σ_{Lmax}^+ with load at mid-section

1. FEM
2. Formula of mechanics of materials,

$$\sigma_{max} = (3PL)/(2bh^2)$$

3-7. Eq.(2),

$$\sigma^0/\sigma_{LB}^- = 1, 0.9, 5/6, 0.7, 5/9, \text{ respectively}$$

Figure 4. Variation of τ_{max} with load at cross-section 7.5 mm from mid-section

1. FEM
2. Formula of mechanics of materials,

$$\tau_{max} = (3P)/(4bh)$$

3-8. Eq.(2),

$$\sigma^0/\sigma_{LB}^- = 1, 0.9, 5/6, 0.7, 5/9, 2/7, \text{ respectively}$$

$$\sigma_{Lmax}^+ = \sigma^0 + \frac{2(-p + \sqrt{p^2 - 4q})}{h - (-p + \sqrt{p^2 - 4q})} \sigma^* , \quad \tau_{max} = \frac{3P}{2b[2h - (-p + \sqrt{p^2 - 4q})]} \quad (2)$$

in which

$$p = \frac{4\sigma^* - 2\sigma^0}{\sigma^0 - \sigma^*} h , \quad q = \frac{\sigma^0 - \frac{3pl}{2bh^2}}{\sigma^0 - \sigma^*} h^2$$

where b and h are the width and thickness of the beam, respectively. σ^0 is the maximum compressive stress in the undamaged portion of the central section of the beam.

In Figures 3 and 4, a comparison between the maximum stresses predicted by Eq.2 and that obtained from numerical computations is presented. The comparison shows that the equations developed can predict the maximum stresses in damaged beam very well. This method is easier to calculate the maximum stresses than the progressive finite element method.

3.3. Toughness

It is well recognized that the failure mechanism of laminated composite materials under impact loading is quite different from that of metals. Hence, it is inadequate to evaluate, as is done for metals, the impact toughness of laminated composite materials based on a notch test. In the case of composites, the crack would change its direction and propagate along the interlaminar at the tip of the notch. Many researchers have studied the dynamic response of composite beams, plates and shells under different impact mass and velocities (7-9). To evaluate the toughness of composites, it is important to record the histories of impact force vs time, and displacement vs time during impact. From these curves, the absorbed energy and its relationship to impact damage can be determined (5).

Figure 5 is the plot of bending stiffness degradation after impact vs the impact energy. From this figure, the energy threshold of damage initiation and the critical energy, at which the stiffness begins to decrease rapidly, can be obtained. It can be observed from Figure 1a that, because both the tensile and compressive strengths of composites in the fiber direction increase with the strain rate, the maximum load reached during impact is greater than that reached during static loading. However, because the interlaminar shear strength does not increase with strain rate, the possibility of shear delamination is increased. Taking this strain rate effect into account, a dynamic strength which is related to the strain rate is

Figure 5. Experimental curve of damage vs impact energy

Figure 6. Simulational curve of stiffness degradation during fatigue

assumed. Following the same procedure as in static case, the peak load as well as the absorbed energy can be determined. For impact loading, comparisons of the results from this model with those from experiments show that the agreement is within about 10 percent.

3.4. Fatigue life

The analysis procedure to predict the fatigue life of three point bending composite beams can be summarized as follows:

- (1) Establish a mesh according to the criteria described earlier.
- (2) Through experiments or from the existing data, establish the relationship between fatigue stress and life of a single layer, the S-N curve.
- (3) Every element is assumed to be under cyclic loading, the amplitude of which is defined by the stress determined by numerical computations. Using the S-N relationship of the layer, identify when and which element will first be damaged.
- (4) Assuming that each damaged element can retain a certain amount of load carrying capacity, calculate the redistribution of stresses in undamaged zone.
- (5) The remaining elements are in fact subjected to either a low-high or high-low spectrum load. Apply a certain accumulative damage rule, such as Miner's linear accumulative damage rule or a similar nonlinear accumulative damage rule, to these elements to identify the subsequent damaged elements.
- (6) Repeat the procedure to determine the complete fatigue damage-failure process for the beam.

The relationship between stiffness degradation and cycle number can be established from these analyses, as indicated in Figure 6 (10). By means of this relationship, the fatigue life can be predicted. The cycle number corresponding to 5-10 percent of the stiffness degradation may be taken as the fatigue life of the beam under the given cyclic loading (11).

4. CONCLUSIONS

This preliminary study shows that, the microdamage and failure modes of unidirectional composite beams subjected to static, low velocity impact and fatigue loading exhibit some similarities. On the basis of the observed similarities, taking into account the specific characteristics of these damage modes, it becomes possible to establish a unified model to determine the stiffness, strength, toughness and fatigue life of unidirectional composite beams. This model, in fact, is a combination of micro and macrofailure theories, and can be utilized in engineering application of composite materials. It is recommended that further studies be conducted to refine the model proposed in this paper. The interaction between

damaged and undamaged elements should be further investigated.

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